

تقویم کے اعتبار سے مقادیر شرعیہ کا تصور

**THE CONCEPT OF SHARIAH MEASURES (MAQADEER)
IN TERM OF VALUATION (TAQWEEM)**

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ABSTRACT

There are many Shariah orders that are linked to measures, weight, valuation, measure of volume, and measure of distance / area (All these measurements are defined by a comprehensive word of Arabic language "Maqadeer"). Therefore, Imam Qarafi says:

"No chapter of jurisprudence is devoid of the statement of Maqadeer."

In order to identify these Maqadeer, during the time of the Prophet (PBUH), special measures of Rital, Mod, Saa, Ziraa, Mile or Farsakh etc. were used. To understand the rulings related to these Shariah measures, it is necessary to know these Shariah Maqadeer, especially known in contemporary scales as well as in common weights and measurements.

For this reason, it has become necessary to conduct in-depth research into these measurement scales in light of the values and arguments of Shariah law. "Taqweem" It is also an important way of finding out about values because it is sometimes impossible to finally determine the value of an object. In that case, the value of the object is measured by expert and just person to avoid difficulties and embarrassment.

No chapter of Islamic jurisprudence is devoid of statements of Taqweem (valuation), such as the determination of the value of the goods for the payment of Zakat, the determination of the value of the perishable articles, evaluating the animal while being hunted by a mohrim, etc.

At the beginning of this article, after going through the definition of evaluation, judgments and related verses, the rules and regulations of evaluation will be mentioned. The impact of being too low or too high is to be evaluated, as well as the need for an expert in setting the price and criteria will also be addressed.

Keywords: Measures, Maqadeer, Valuation, Taqweem, Islamic Jurisprudence.

کلیدی الفاظ: مقادیر، تقویم، شرعیہ، اسلامی فقہ، اسلامی قانون۔

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